

Parental Authorization – Minors

The project “SOCPacific2R - A Sea of Connections: Valuing Reef Passages in the South Pacific Region”, led by researchers from the University of the South Pacific (USP), the French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD), and the Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research (ZMT), is both an interdisciplinary research and educational project. One of its objectives is to understand, through various productions (such as drawings and oral or written descriptions), children’s representations, knowledges, and practices concerning reef passages. These data will feed into a scientific database.

I, the undersigned:

Full name:

As the parent or legal guardian of the child:

Full name:

Date of birth:

Address:

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Hereby confirm that I grant the following authorizations:

1. Authorization for Participation in the SOCPacific2R Project

I authorize the above-mentioned child to participate in the child-oriented activities proposed by the SOCPacific2R project (such as drawing workshops or discussion sessions on reef passages and land-sea connections).

Yes

No

Signature of the parent or legal guardian:

2. Authorization for the Scientific Use of Children’s Works (of art and other)

I hereby authorize and assign to USP, IRD, and ZMT all rights of representation and reproduction pertaining to the works (such as drawings and written or oral descriptions) to which the above-mentioned child has contributed as part of the SOCPacific2R project, for use in the activities described above, valid worldwide and for the entire duration of the legal protection of such rights.

Yes

No

Signature of the parent or legal guardian:

3. Authorization for the Use of Image

I authorize USP, IRD, and ZMT to use images (photographs, videos, films) of the above-mentioned child, taken as part of the SOCPacific2R project, in order to communicate about these scientific and educational activities, free of charge, worldwide and for the entire duration of the legal protection, on all media (press, publications, exhibitions, websites, social media, electronic and audiovisual formats).

Yes

No

Signature of the parent or legal guardian:

Data Protection Provisions (GDPR)

The personal data collected (name, contact details, image, etc.) will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU - 2016/679).

You have the right to access, rectify, erase, and restrict the processing of the above-mentioned child's personal data. You may exercise these rights or lodge a complaint by writing to IRD's data protection officer at the following address: dpo@ird.fr